

ANALYSIS OF GERIATRIC DEPRESSION THOUGHTS AMONG INSTITUTIONALIZED SENIOR CITIZENS

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Abstract:

The process of growing older is known as ageing. Humans, many animals, and fungi are among the species that are physiologically not immortal, although bacteria, perennial plants, and certain simple animals are not. Aging can refer to solitary cells inside an organism that have stopped dividing (cellular senescence) or the population of a species in a larger sense (population ageing). It applies to human beings also.

Introduction:

Because of the issues that the formal and informal care systems are facing, the number of older people with unmet care and support requirements is on the rise. Addressing the unmet care and support requirements of an ageing population, as well as providing services and solutions that are centred on what older people need or desire, is quickly becoming a top public health concern (Abdi, Spann, Borilovic, Witte, & Hawley, 2019).

Ageing in humans refers to the gradual accumulation of changes in a person's physical, psychological, and social characteristics through time. For example, reaction speed may reduce as people get older, although knowledge of current events and wisdom may increase. Aging is one of the most well-known risk factors for the majority of human illnesses. About two-thirds of the 150,000 people who die every day throughout the world-100,000 per day-die from age-related causes. The proportion is larger in developed countries, exceeding 90%. Numerous physical, psychological, and social role changes confront these people, challenging their sense of self and ability to live joyfully (Singh, A., & Misra, N, 2009).

Most of the problems were hidden in the senior citizens and need counselling to ventilate. This can be done using Social Work Interventions. This article tries to know some of the thoughts which arise out of the aged people. These thoughts are analysed using the opinions given by the senior citizens who are institutionalized. In India the citizens who are above 60 years are referred as senior citizens.

Research Methodology:

This is a small study. Descriptive research design has been used for this study. The sampling was purposive sampling. Required data collected using structured interview schedule. 30 senior citizens were interviewed to collect data. 20 male senior citizens and 10 female senior citizens were taken for the study. Samples were taken from an Old Age Home in Mysuru of Karnataka State and the name of the institution is kept confidential because of the request from the administrators of the institution.

Geriatric Depression Thoughts

S.No	Questions	Female		Male	
		Yes	No	Yes	No
1	Are you satisfied with your life	6	4	16	4
2	Have you dropped many of your activities and interests	6	4	12	8
3	Do you feel that your life is empty	4	6	2	18
4	Do you often get bored?	2	8	4	16
5	Are you in good spirits most of the time?	6	4	10	10
6	Are you afraid that something bad is going to happen to you	2	8	6	14
7	Do you feel happy most of the time?	4	6	12	8
8	Do you often feel helpless?	0	10	8	12
9	Do you prefer to stay at home, rather than going out and doing something?	2	8	6	14
10	Do you feel you have more problems with memory than most	4	6	8	12
11	Do you feel it is wonderful to be alive now?	2	8	6	14
12	Do you feel that your situation is hopeless	2	8	2	18
13	Do you think that most people are better off than you are	4	6	4	16

Many elderly individuals suffer from loneliness and depression, either as a consequence of living alone or as a result of a loss of close family relationships and diminished links to their culture of origin, resulting in an inability to actively participate in community activities (Singh, A., & Misra, N, 2009). This article has been written to find out whether the senior citizens have encountered problems like satisfaction with the life, dropped interest in the life, do they feel empty or bored, or they lose spirit of life etc...

While analysing, the study, it is found that 6 females (20%) and 16 males (53.33%) of the males are satisfied with their life. This is because most of the male senior citizens have achieved Maslow's Hierarchy of

Needs. 6 female senior citizens (20%) and 12 male senior citizens (40%) dropped many of their activities and interest. This may be attributed to the ageing process, there will be a decrease in physical activity and functional fitness for both men and women (Milanović et al., 2013).

4 females (13.33%) and 2 males (6.67%) feel that their life is empty. 2 females (6.67%) and 4 males (13.33%) got bored. 6 females (20%) and 10 males (33.33%) are in a good spirits most of the time. Senior citizens frequently suffer from sadness and anxiety, and boredom is a major contributor. As people get older, they may feel lonely and isolated, and boredom just adds to that feeling. We all require self-worth, but we probably don't know how perilous it may be for senior citizens to deal with the impacts of boredom-induced lack of purpose (Jurica, 2018)

2 females (6.67%) and 6 males (20%) are afraid of something bad is going to happen to them. 4 females (13.33%) and 12 males (40%) feel happy most of the time. Only 8 males (26.67%) often feel helpless. 2 females (6.67%) and 6 males (20%) prefer to stay at home rather than going out and doing something. 4 females (13.33) and 8 males (26.67%) felt that they have memory problems. 2 females (6.67%) and 6 males (20%) feel that it is wonderful to be alive now. 2 females (6.67%) and 2 males (6.67%) feel that their situation is hopeless. 4 females (13.33%) and 4 males (13.33%) think that most people are better off than them. According to various studies conducted throughout the world, one of the most severe issues confronting elderly is that they frequently feel neglected, alienated, and hence dejected and dissatisfied. Finding ways for the elderly to feel joyful and so find meaning in life is the remedy to the problem. It's difficult to say what makes a person happy since the factors that influence happiness varies from person to person. It is determined by a person's genetics, environment, and attitude toward life and its numerous aspects (Gupta, 2021) .

Problems Faced by the Investigator:

The investigator encountered certain problems like when visited institutions, in the beginning they were not ready to ventilate their thoughts and problems. Sometimes they were explaining some of the issues which are not related to this research. Availability of the website posts are more compared to empirical journal articles.

Conclusion:

Age related problems add one by one as the age passes. Some senior citizens share their thoughts and some senior citizens fail to share. There are various reasons for these problems, one thing is adults do not heed to their problems, because people always want to be with their contemporary. Most of the senior citizens are in a good spirit. Male senior show less problems compared to their female counterparts. This is because gender has its specific problems. More than half of the senior citizens are satisfied with their life. This was due to most male senior citizens having achieved Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Some of the senior citizens also expressed that they need counselling to come out of some of the problems. Some problems need Social Work intervention. So we need more interventions from Social Work Methods. Hope we do more research in the future and find out problems which are hidden in the senior citizens and find out solutions.

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